

A study on active ingredients of a new chemotype of *Ocimum sanctum*

Souvik Santra^a, Pulak Gangopadhyay^{a*} and Shibnath Ghosal^b

^aDepartment of Chemistry, Ramakrishna Mission Residential College Narendrapur, Kolkata-700 103, India

E-mail : pulakganguly@yahoo.co.in

^bNatreon-Inc. (India), CL-18A, Salt Lake, Kolkata-700 091, India

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Abstract : A new chemotype of *Ocimum sanctum* bearing high terpene constituents of immunomodulatory potential has been discovered.

Keywords : Chemotype, *Ocimum sanctum*, β -caryophyllene, immunomodulator, immunostimulator.

Introduction

Medicinal plants are a major source of drugs for the treatment of various health disorders in rural areas of Indian sub continent. The use of plant based medicines dates back to 4000-5000 B.C. According to assessment of WHO about 80% of world population depends on medicinal plants for their health-care needs and more than 30% of the pharmaceutical preparations are based on plants¹. But very few systematic research has been made for the bioactive quality assessment of these plants through extraction, isolation and characterization of their active ingredients. The primary objective of our study was qualitative and quantitative determinations of active ingredients of a specific chemotype of Tulsi (*Ocimum sanctum*)²⁻⁶ which Ramakrishna Mission Ashrama (RKMA), Narendrapur is cultivating and using for the treatment of patients suffering from different types of syndromes associated with oxidative stress. This research on the quality of this important medicinal plant would suggest the importance of standardization of the cultivated plants and the inefficiency factor of wild-crafted plants normally available in the commercial market.

Results and discussion

Extensive HPTLC determinations established the following. The preponderance of terpenes in the new chemotype sample (RKMA) of tulsi was evident from the chromatographic and spectroscopic analyses of the terpenes (74%) (hexane-soluble fraction of the methanol extract) versus percentage of terpenes observed with standard marketed sample (IH) of tulsi (hexane-soluble frac-

tion of the methanol extract) (26%). Thus, about 3 times higher concentration of total terpenes was observed in the new chemotype *O. sanctum* (leaves) grown in RKMA.

By contrast, the contents of eugenol in the methanol extracts, of the two types of *O. sanctum* extracts were reversed. While in the methanol extracts of the marketed sample of tulsi (IH), the amount of eugenol was 9.94%, this phenolic compound occurred to the extent of only 1.56% (w/w) in the new chemotype tulsi (RKMA variety). Free eugenol, with overt phenolic character can not efficiently combat oxidative stress. β -Caryophyllene, by contrast acts as a potent immunomodulator and anti-oxidant factor⁷⁻⁹.

The identity of the major terpenes and the phenolics were further confirmed by GC-MS analysis (Table 1). The GC-MS data also indicated very large difference in the contents of the terpenes and of eugenol in the two types of tulsi (RKMA vs IH) (*Ocimum sanctum* leaves). There is no substantial difference in the chemical characters of the two types of tulsi; they vary in the relative abundance of the bioactives.

The new chemotype of tulsi differ from wild-crafted one in the relative abundance of the mevalonate derived terpenes and DOPA-derived eugenol.

The significance of the high terpene-yielding chemotype, *O. santum*, can be projected in the light of immunomodulatory role^{10,11} of the contained terpenes. The methanol extract of the new chemotype (RKMA), dose dependently, proliferated and inhibited rat-splenic lymphocytes, suggesting its immunomodulatory potential. High eugenol

Table 1. Comparative GC-MS analysis of new chemotype (RKMA) and standard marketed (IH) tulsi extract

t_R (min)	Name of compound	Tulsi extract	
		Standard sample (IH)	Tulsi extract (New chemotype) (RKMA)
		% w/w	% w/w
20.735	Eugenol	9.94	1.56
21.637	β -Caryophyllene	1.70	0.19
22.374	Benzene, 1-(1,5-dimethyl-4-hexenyl)-4-methyl-	1.09	2.21
22.450	Di-epi- α -cedrene	1.89	0.77
22.495	Azulene, 1,2,3,3a,4,5,6,7-octahydro-1,4-dimethyl-7-(1-methylethenyl)-	1.51	0.97
22.653	Cedrene	1.00	1.43
23.301	Caryophyllene oxide	0.37	0.15
23.903	Phenol, 4,6-di-(1,1-dimethylethyl)-2-methyl-	0.25	0.32

yielding variety (IH), in contrast exhibited immuno-stimulatory action in the tested doses (5–80 mcg/ml).

Experimental

Techniques and conditions :

HPTLC :

Camag TLC evaluation software (CATS V_{4.05}) was used; plate material, silica gel 60 F₂₅₄; application mode, Camag linomat-IV; development mode, Camag twin chamber; developer, toluene : ethylacetate (97 : 3); detection mode, deuterium lamp, wavelength, 264 nm; staining reagent, anisaldehyde-sulphuric acid.

GC-MS :

Varian GC-MS, model Saturn-2000, detection type 3800; column V A-5 (5% phenyl)-methyl polysiloxane (30 m × 0.2 mm i.d.); GC condition Column programme, gradual increase in temperature from 150 °C (1 min hold) @ 5 °C/min upto 210 °C (4 min hold), again rise @ 5 °C/min upto 240 °C (6 min hold), and finally by 10 °C/min up to 260 °C (4 min hold); flow rate, 1 ml/min; carrier gas, helium; EI-MS ionization potential 70 eV.

Extraction of plant material :

Ocimum sanctum leaves of the cultivated variety were collected in January 2008, from The Medicinal Plant Gar-

den of RKMA, Narendrapur. A specimen has been preserved as a reference in our file. The fresh leaves (ca. 1 kg) was macerated in methanol and the mixture was kept at room temperature overnight and then filtered.

The solvent was evaporated from the methanol extract under reduced pressure to give a gummy residue (150 g). It was triturated with *n*-hexane to give hexane soluble (90 g) and hexane insoluble (60 g) material. A similar procedure was followed with *O. sanctum* marketed sample of Indian Herbs Ltd. (IH), Saharanpur to give an extractive (135 g) of which 40% (54 g) was hexane soluble and 60% (81 g) was hexane insoluble. The methanol soluble and hexane soluble extracts of the two varieties of *O. sanctum* leaves were subjected to comprehensive chromatographic (HPTLC and GC) and spectroscopic (MS) analyses. The results are given in the text and Table 1.

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